

Agroecological zoning of the Red River plain.

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Information flow from farmers in extension training and visit system: a case of rice production recommendations

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Extension organizations are concerned with the transfer of information from experiment stations to farmers. Diffusion and adoption of recommendations have been used to assess the effectiveness of extension methods used. But practical problems faced by farmers are often not conveyed to scientists.

The Training and Visit (T&V) system of agricultural extension attempts to

Main channels for backward flow of information in the T&V extension system in Sri Lanka.^a

Extension recommendations	Main farmer-to-extension contacts (backward flow) (%)			No "backward" contact (%)
	VEVs	CFs	FFs	
Variety	41	14	12	33
Transplanting methods	48	11	14	27
Fertilizer use	34	14	12	40
Chemical pest control	30	10	24	36
Chemical disease control	28	08	20	44

^an = 100 farmers.

address this drawback. In the T&V system, information is passed from village extension workers (VEVs) to contact farmers (CFs), then to follower farmers (FFs). Information also flows in the other direction, from farmers back to extension workers and to researchers.

In Sri Lanka, one VEW is assigned to 36 CFs, and one CF is responsible for 21 farmers. CFs are expected to perform a

catalyzing role, so that agricultural information can be more widely disseminated to farmers. Ideally, CFs also convey farmer queries, problems, and needs back to the VEVs (in a process of "backward flow").

We investigated the backward flow of information about selected rice production recommendations in Matara district, southern Sri Lanka, in a survey of 100

randomly selected rice farmers (see table).

For the five types of recommendations examined, more farmers tended to contact their VEWs. Some farmers also consult FFs regarding chemical pest and disease control recommendations, perhaps because farmers in adjacent

fields have similar problems and timely actions are essential to control such outbreaks.

For all recommendations, few inquiries were made to CFs, and this link seems to be ineffective in the process of two-way communication. Overall, feedback to research was limited. ■

ANNOUNCEMENT

Direct-seeded rice technology

Direct-seeded rice, principles and practices, by K. N. Singh and H. C. Bhattacharyya, consolidates information on direct seeding, an alternative to transplanting. The chapters describe direct

seeding practices in various parts of the world, discuss technologies for the practice, and point out future research areas. The book was published by Oxford & IBP Publishing Co., Pvt. Ltd., 66 Janpath, New Delhi 1 10001, India. That company should be contacted for ordering information. ■

ERRATA

Decline of morphogenic in microspore-derived calli from indica/japonica and japonica/japonica F₁ hybrids, by E. Guiderdoni, J. Luistro, and G. Vergara. 15(2) (Apr 1990), 6-7.

On page 7, column 2, line 9, change Kelef/IRAT216 to IR64/IRAT216; in line 13, change 10% to 1%. ■

An IRI3240-108-4-2-3 line with leaf blast (B1) and brown planthopper (BP11) biotype 2 resistance in Angiang, Vietnam, by Le Hieu Huu, Nguyen Thuan Khiet, and Vo Van Mieng. 15 (1) (Feb 1990), 19.

In the title and in the first line of paragraph I, IRI3240-108-4-2-3 should read IRI3240-108-2-2-3. ■
